

Searching for Meaning in Dying

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The theme I have chosen to explore as my mode of discourse over the topic of life and death is the one on the philosophy of death. I have come to realise that death is sometimes looked at as a negative outcome in one's journey of life. It is a concept that paves into too many ambiguities and is perceived differently in unfathomable numbers of belief systems all across the world. There have been many prevailing accounts on the conception of death throughout the course of history, and to summarise a well-versed understanding on how it is conceptualised and integrated into cultures, I felt it was necessary to build my own perspective upon the same. To explore what it means to me, I felt I needed to conduct my research on those who illuminated the idea of death through the course of their work and lives. In my opinion, there wouldn't have been a more accurate account of the representation of death, than those coming from two philosophers whose work entailed pieces that added to the process of understanding what it is.

I have to be honest in saying that their works did not prove any conclusive statements, nor did they entertain any pre-conceived notions that may find themselves surrounding the

talk of death. I did not find anything that spoke of a definite afterlife, or even anything about semi-conscious post-natal states. I did, however, learn a lot about how to formulate my worldview and use what I know today to serve as a means to understand what to expect of what I don't know. Researching on these philosophers helped me in rationalising the realities of life, identifying with who I am as a person and what death means to me. I don't look for meaning where there isn't any to find, although I can confidently say that death does play a very important role in how one leads one's life. I realised there are some ground-rules to remember when attempting to conceptualise something as vague as death. I hope this essay bifurcates from the ambiguities of life, paying emphasis on how to distinguish a rational understanding of the same.

The main objective of my research is to find meaning to the idea of death. I feel death is an unexplored means of human action, it can be viewed as an essential characteristic to add meaning into one's life. I believe death makes way for life, and hence cannot be deemed negative. In order to assess its true nature, I chose to include the works of two notable philosophers who have devoted their lives in developing an authentic account of this concept. I feel as if death when left open to debate can stimulate ambiguous representations that may vary in their accuracy. When I say that, I imply it in terms of their capability in assimilating and graphing the sophistications that lie in such an unexplored aspect. I have used all of their most established works and tried to correlate them into a conclusion I have come to happenstance by myself. The aim of the essay is to derive a more conclusive account of life, something that offers the reader with a little more specification on the dos and don'ts of life and existence, and how to make the most of one's predicament.

Paul Ricoeur, revered for his work in the field of continental philosophy talks in his works about death, immortality, life, mortality and natality. In engaging perceptions on what it means to live, and arguments about how death can only be through life - ergo only be defined through life, he takes us through his beliefs on what it means to lead a nourishing life. In his final work, *living up to death*, explains how the act of death is an act of life since death is the elimination of life thereby disengaging from the idea of an afterlife. He too draws inspiration from the works of other scholars such as Sigmund Freud, and adds his insight on the idealism of the works of mourning and detachment, two subsidiaries that consequence the act of death. Here, detachment is described as letting go of the attachment to/off any object, the loss of which is equivalent to the loss of self. This brackets off imaginary projection of an afterlife or any form of personal resurrection. Through my essay, I aim to supplement a breakdown of all the writings and claims made on this ideology.

Martin Heidegger, another continental philosopher born in Nazi Germany offers an alternative approach to the idealisms surrounding life, death and the things that lie in between. His evaluation of death is drawn primarily from his work *Being and Time*, in which he discusses the relevance of self-identity and the significance of time in its development. He views death as a taboo for a topic, refrained from being open to discussion by the likes of those he deems to be cowards i.e., people incapable of understanding death in its most natural sense. He broadly explains how the body is learning death from the moment it is formed, using analogies such as the ripening of a fruit. The subjectivity of death lies in the intricacies of the being, and Heidegger argues that a more logical approach to death would be embracing it for its nature and using it to focus on one's own existence. Heidegger, I find,

has a rather uplifting approach towards death as it is only in relation to death that one truly becomes aware of one's freedom.

Ricoeur claims that the idea following a narrative decipher the crux of one's arrival to one's own identity. We are in the constant ebb and flow of a story that we continue to create till we die, and we are all its characters and themes. Even if the story isn't our own, to derive something significant from the story that superimposes meaning onto our own lives, is the aim of such narrative. In effect, narrative identity helps one encounter answers to questions that appraise and validate life; "who am I? where am I going?"

The narrative sets us in the path of assertion of the self. Whether the self is a physical, turgid, conscious entity or whether the self is a metaphysical, passive, subconscious one is solely reliant on the narrative we see it through. It then has the capability of being both abstract or limited. His argument proceeds through several different layers of thought. The first acknowledgment of the self is through the language used in its narrative, identifying the facilitator of it as an agent of life passing through the semantics of action. Then after is asserting the self through one's narrative identity, and this is followed by the ethical ramifications that lie within what makes the self. It means to ask and acknowledge what is "I" and when is "I", which is lived through conviction rather than scientific certainty.

If Martin Heidegger's work *Being and Time* has taught us anything, it is the fact that death has been a tabooed or under-spoken means of discourse over time due to its inexplicable and nonfigurative nature. His use of language through this work is a slave to its time, making it a product of an innovative means of discussion. What I have chosen to consider

for my research is a segment of this work which illuminates Heidegger's take on death as an unexplored characteristic of existence. To understand one's existence as a whole, one must differentiate the authentic self from the inauthentic self. One's life shifts its focus through the narrative chosen by oneself. To justify its use, one must choose to process thought in its most authentic form.

Heidegger, in his own writings has managed to address issues surrounding immortality, life after death and the nature of death during one's own existence. He includes death as a prerequisite to life, just as is, one could argue, the case with war and peace. He implies man is a whole entity called Existence or Dasein. Existence, through his death, comes aware of the finite nature of his being, ultimately realizing why he has been termed existence. Existentialism is the outcome of the acceptance of death as a characteristic of life. As, it is only through one's own existence, that one can provide life with meaning and definition. This argument diverges into subsidiary philosophies that may argue against any actualized, uniform and unanimous definitions. This is because I can only claim to know what I have come to know through my own time and place on this planet. Only through my own existence and being can I cast a notion or definition of and on something. Thus, it is only one's existence that is then actualized, uniform and unanimous.

“Expression is existence”. To conceptualize hermeneutics into Paul Ricoeur's understanding of it, one must accept the notion that his work is contemporary and that he deems it to transcend the barricades of culture and time. He regards hermeneutics to be a moderm of self-actualization and self-understanding. He claims both explicitly and implicitly that in order to develop this understanding of the

self, one must understand what surrounds this self. Thus, self-comprehension is derived from comprehending others. One's existence is arranged in a chronological, linear setting. We compartmentalize the events of our lives with the help of such a setting to formulate a more organized flow of thought. There is a beginning, an ongoing and an ending. All of what we know fits through these quantifications, and what is unknown to us is what lies beyond them. Through the means of others who have existed before us, ergo, expressed before us – we generate meaning to life. Through the lives and expressions of what those before us have left behind, we build notions and meanings that support our understanding of our own existence.

With regards to death, it isn't something one can express. But as we all come to know in different, unique ways of our own, death can be left behind through experiences of those who came before us. One of the most relevant themes that can be found in Ricoeur's writings is that of philosophical anthropology. He devised an idea around what he considered to be a capable human being. Through his work, he strives to generate a comprehensive account of the vulnerabilities, inhibitions, talents and capabilities that humans display through the course of their lives. He categorizes these activities as relevant to sustaining their coexistence as a species and terms them as responsible human action. Although he tries to create an understanding to the notion of what becomes the self, he claims that this identity is reserved and not transparent to its proprietor. The self can only be made apparent through the relationship the proprietor has shared with what surrounds them, their relationship with the world and its cohabitants.

To come to these conclusions, Ricoeur often shifted the themes in his discourse in order to categorize his intellectual

settings to adjust to new developments. Often, questioning and challenging his own work, he practiced reflexive thought to broaden the spectrum of questions asked about the field of his study. Most of his initial publications were either the product of war, or came about to be during them. From what he had learnt in his academic years, he came to understand how the “I” or self, comes aware, creates meaning, thinks, acts and ultimately exits through reflexive consciousness.

Although Dasein or The Self cannot experience its own death as actual, what it can do is always know its inevitability, and therefore be before it. That is, to embrace the idea of death before it limits physical existence to achieve metaphysical freedom. Dasein cannot confirm death, only avail its possibility since after death, there is no Dasein. Death then, through Dasein, can be defined as “possibility of the impossibility of any existence at all”. Through the omnipresence of death around Dasein, one must acknowledge death as a means of non-relationality, that is to cut all ties from everything. This stems from the radicle implication that one’s death is one’s own. It is through this acknowledgment of one’s non-existence that one can engage in the ability of being-able-to-be to not-being at all. Awareness of one’s own death as an omnipresent possibility discloses one’s most honest predicament. It is here when one can deliberate the most authentic version of the self. Dasein too, then is a finite being.

This awareness towards one’s death creates a realization of a concept coined as being-toward-death. It is to live through recognizing death. Anxiety here is not necessarily considered as a negative characteristic to the make of the being, but rather a provider of the knowledge needed to carry out decisions made around one’s existence. This gives rise to the authentic and the inauthentic birth of the self. When

the self is anxious, it sees the world as intangible. Here, the possibilities of the world moving forward without the self are brought to light along with the ontological sense of not-being or un-being and the acceptance of 'nothing' as an outcome. This is the authentic self.

The inauthentic self, deals with evasion of such concepts. Here the self considers it to be of higher significance by abstaining death from adding meaning into its existence. This does not mean that one would disregard the possibility of one's own death, rather, it is to operate without computing the certainty of death through one's actions. To validate this, one's own death cannot ever be witnessed by them. Therefore, it isn't incorrect to say I will never experience my own death. In my metaphysical understanding of the concept, I can live forever through my own perspective.

Inauthenticity of the self can also come through fear. Fear of the notion of death can generate fake responses, as it is to live as if one is experiencing death when in reality, one isn't. This is contrasting to anxiety, which is to perceive a world without oneself. Let me use an example to explain this difference more appropriately. When I go to a bar in the attempt to try a new kind of cocktail, I can either anticipate the flavor of my drink or I can expect the flavor of my drink. What happens here is, when I expect the flavor of my drink, I am waiting for an actual sequence of events to occur. I have already asserted my cocktail with a quality. However, if I anticipate its taste, it is making me aware of the possibility of how it may taste. So, in a cognitive sense, I go out to meet that possibility - thus owning that experience. Expecting death is waiting for a death to happen, anticipating one's death is owning it.

The Dasein is a finite being. If we were infinite, immortal

beings, learning would happen directly. We wouldn't have to pour hours of time pondering away at the complexities of our own existence, but rather learn them as they are. Since we are finite beings, our learning happens indirectly. We learn through metaphors or connotations or abstractions or vagueness. Our learning is interpretational, and meaning to things change with the ebb and flow of time. We do not have a definitive understanding of anything, let alone death. What we can do is learn through the example of others. In a nihilistic point of view, we can argue that death is the outcome to all existence, it is what completes life's journey and gives it meaning. Life can be considered a fable wherein the way you die defines the purpose of your being, it can be looked at as the moral of one's story. To fully assess what it means to have died a significant death, one must live a significant life. The judge of this significance is based solely on what is derived off the experiences one has endured. The indirect learning here can either satisfy one's existence or contradict it. But in the case of life, there are almost never any binaries. There is never a definitive good or a definitive bad. It's not black, nor white, but a colossal amount of grey. Death to me has always been an area that stirs much debate. I have read plenty on its cause and effects, its nature, its nurture. Something as limiting as death can be enough for one to fully explore the potential that lies within one's existence, however, we are so caught up in trying to justify our deaths that we forget living.

“Pain is temporary” was one of the last things that were said to me before the passing of an individual I held very dearly. There is so little and yet so much in that said phrase, maybe the timing of which makes it all the more profound. It is a statement that holds true throughout age and tide. Pain is another aspect of life, along with death, love and

happiness. Pain is growth, and one can only become more through pain. Death can cause pain, which can cause growth. Pain is temporary, as is life. The finite nature of being and time was exposed through a phrase, that at the time of it being said, could have meant nothing. Maybe because I have come to address this loss, and because this was said to me very close to the departure of this individual, I have read more into it. But maybe that is the point of one's narrative or Dasein. Maybe, the means through which one can achieve immortality is through insignificant phrases like this said at significant times. Or maybe it could be through creation and procreation. We have come to understand how ideologies may live on forever, but I feel ideologies then are what you may intend to make of them. The subjective nature of information processing dwindles the possibility of any particular criteria from staying relevant.

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of the Bombay Province of the Society of Jesus for their help and encouragement by supplying us with the relevant materials.

The Title, *Melodies from the Flute*

Indeed, this book is a tribute to Noel Sheth from his colleagues and friends. We affirm that Noel has tirelessly worked for inter-religious dialogue, has attempted dialogue between science and religion and has assiduously sought for wisdom deeply rooted in our Indian traditions and the Christian heritage!

(Bibliography Details: Pandikattu, Kuruvila and Thomas Kari-mundackal (eds) *Melodies from the Flute: Dialogue Among Religions and Cultures : Memorial Volume for Indian Christian Philosopher Rev Noel Sheth SJ.* , New Delhi: Christian World Imprints, 2018 ISBN: 978-93-5148-325-0 (HB) pp. 332+xvii.)